

Analysis of Single Lap Adhesive Composite Joints with Delaminated Adherends

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SUMMARY: The beam theory is used to model single lap adhesive composite joints with delaminated adherends. Variation of the strain energy release rate with delamination size in the joints with unidirectional and cross-ply adherends is calculated and analyzed. Growth of delaminations of different initial size is studied experimentally and compared with the results of calculation. Experimental observations are found to corroborate with theoretical predictions.

KEYWORDS: Adhesive Bonding, Single Lap Joints, Delamination, Strain Energy Release Rate

INTRODUCTION

Polymer matrix composites are used in repair of aerospace structures. Adhesively bonded composite patches are capable of minimizing balance and clearance problems on control surfaces and can be readily formed to complex aircraft contours. Reinforcement in a patch can be tailored to suit the loading configuration and to minimize undesirable stiffness increase. Delamination in adherends is one of the major damage modes in adhesive composite joints. Delamination may occur during manufacturing of joints or in service due to substantial interlaminar peel and shear stresses developed in the adherends near the overlap edges. Growth of delamination in the adherends of a single lap adhesive composite joint is addressed in this work.

Substantial effort was devoted over the years to elastic analysis of adhesive joints. Goland and Reissner, in their classical paper [1], analyzed stress distributions in the adhesive layer of a single lap joint. It was shown that both peel and shear stresses in the adhesive layer could be very large. The peel stress is induced by the overall load eccentricity and is especially significant at the edges of the overlap. These large out-of-plane stresses can result in delamination of composite adherends. To date, little effort was devoted to the analysis of joints with delaminated adherends. Williams [2] used the beam theory to calculate the strain energy release rate for cracked laminates. The strain energy release rate was defined in terms of the membrane forces, transverse shear forces, and bending moments at the crack tip. Recently, Tong et al. [3] used the modified approach [2] to calculate the strain energy release rate for a single lap adhesive joint with cracked unidirectional adherends. It was shown that the strain energy release rate decreased as the

crack length increased. No information is available on the behavior of joints with cracked laminated adherends.

In this paper, the model [3] is generalized for joints with delaminated adherends of arbitrary lay-up. Variation of the strain energy release rate with delamination size in the joints with unidirectional and cross-ply adherends is calculated and analyzed. Experimental verification of the model predictions is performed for the first time.

MODEL FORMULATION

Consider a single lap adhesive composite joints with arbitrary laminated adherends (Figure1). The adherends have the same lay-up, thickness t , and the same free length l . The overlap length of the joint is $2c$. A delamination embedded between the plies in the adherend has the tip A inside the joint overlap and the tip B outside the joint overlap. Figures 2 and 3 show the stress resultants acting in the cross sections at the crack tips A and B , respectively.

Figure 1. A single lap adhesive composite joint with a crack

Figure 2. Stress resultants acting on the cross section of the crack tip A

The stress resultants acting in the lower and upper parts of the cracked adherend in the cross section at the crack tip A can be calculated as follows [3]:

Figure 3. Stress resultants acting on the cross section of the crack tip B

$$\begin{aligned}
 M_{A1} &= \mathbf{x}^3 M_0 - \mathbf{x} Q_0 l_A + \frac{t_1}{2} \int_{c-l_A}^c \mathbf{t}(x) dx - \int_{c-l_A}^c \mathbf{s}(x)(x - c - l_A) dx \\
 Q_{A1} &= \mathbf{x} Q_0 + \int_{c-l_A}^c \mathbf{s}(x) dx \\
 P_{A1} &= \mathbf{x} P_0 + 6\mathbf{x}(1 - \mathbf{x}) M_0 / t + \int_{c-l_A}^c \mathbf{t}(x) dx \\
 M_{A1} &= (1 - \mathbf{x})^3 M_0 - (1 - \mathbf{x}) Q_0 l_A \\
 Q_{A2} &= (1 - \mathbf{x}) Q_0 \\
 P_{A2} &= (1 - \mathbf{x})(P_0 - 6\mathbf{x} M_0 / t) \\
 \mathbf{x} &= t_1 / t
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

where $\mathbf{s}(x)$ and $\mathbf{t}(x)$ are the peel and shear stresses in the adhesive layer. M_0 and Q_0 are the bending moment and the transverse shear force at the end of the overlap. These are given by the modified method [1].

The stress resultants acting in the lower and upper parts of the cracked adherend in the cross section at the crack tip B are defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 M_{B1} &= \mathbf{x}^3 M_B \\
 Q_{B1} &= \mathbf{x} Q_B \\
 P_{B1} &= \mathbf{x} P_B + 6\mathbf{x}(1 - \mathbf{x}) M_B / t \\
 M_{B2} &= (1 - \mathbf{x})^3 M_B \\
 Q_{B2} &= (1 - \mathbf{x}) Q_B \\
 P_{B2} &= (1 - \mathbf{x}) P_B - 6\mathbf{x}(1 - \mathbf{x}) M_B / t \\
 \mathbf{x} &= t_1 / t
 \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

M_B and Q_B are obtained by using the modified solution [1].

The total strain energy release rate at the delamination tips is calculated as a sum of the

energy release rates caused by the bending moments, shear forces, and membrane forces, respectively. These rates are defined for adherends with arbitrary lay-up [2] as:

$$G = G_M + G_Q + G_P \quad (3)$$

where G_M , G_Q and G_P are the energy release rates caused by bending moments, shear forces and membrane forces respectively.

The G_M , G_Q and G_P for adherends with arbitrary lay-up can be expressed as follows [2]:

$$\begin{aligned} G_M &= \frac{1}{2}d_{11}^{(1)}M_1^2 + \frac{1}{2}d_{11}^{(2)}M_2^2 - \frac{1}{2}d_{11}(M_1 + M_2)^2 \\ G_Q &= \sum_{i=1}^{n_1} \frac{1}{G_i} \int_{z_{i-1}}^{z_i} \left[\frac{3Q_1}{4t_1} \left(1 - \frac{z^2}{t_1} \right) \right]^2 dz + \sum_{i=1}^{n_2} \frac{1}{G_i} \int_{z_{i-1}}^{z_i} \left[\frac{3Q_2}{4t_2} \left(1 - \frac{z^2}{t_2} \right) \right]^2 dz - \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{G_i} \int_{z_{i-1}}^{z_i} \left[\frac{3(Q_1 + Q_2)}{4t} \left(1 - \frac{z^2}{t} \right) \right]^2 dz \\ G_P &= \frac{1 - \mathbf{n}_2 \mathbf{n}_3}{2} \left[\sum_{i=1}^{n_1} \frac{(P_1/n_1)^2}{E_i t_1} + \sum_{i=1}^{n_2} \frac{(P_2/n_2)^2}{E_i t_2} - \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{((P_1 + P_2)/n)^2}{E_i t} \right] \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where $d_{11}^{(1)}$, $d_{11}^{(2)}$, and d_{11} are bending stiffnesses, n_1 , n_2 and n are ply numbers for the lower and upper sublaminates and the total laminate, respectively, E_i is the Young's modulus E_x and G_i is the shear modulus G_{xz} of the i -th ply. Note that the mode partitioning of the total energy performed in [2] appears to be incorrect according to the results in [4]. Therefore, only the total energy is analyzed in this work.

NUMERICAL ANALYSIS

The model described above was used to calculate the strain energy release rate in single lap joints with adherends made of Hexcel T2G_190-12"-F263 graphite-epoxy composite. Unidirectional $[0]_6$ and cross-ply $[0/90/0]_8$ adherends were analyzed. The mechanical properties of the graphite-epoxy ply were $E_{11}=132.7$ GPa, $E_{22}=E_{33}=8.83$ GPa, $\mathbf{n}_2=\mathbf{n}_3=0.36$, $G_{12}=4.76$ GPa. The ply thickness was 0.1875 mm. The joint had the free length 150 mm and the overlap length 60 mm.

Figure 4 compares the total strain energy release rate at the crack tip A inside the overlap for the joints with unidirectional and cross-ply adherends. The delamination was located between the first and second plies nearest to the adhesive layer. The far-field tensile stress in the adherends of the joint was 220 MPa. It is seen that in both cases, the strain energy release rate dissipates with the increasing crack length. The maximum strain energy release rate for the cross-ply joint is higher than the maximum energy release rate for the unidirectional joint. However, it decreases faster as the delamination grows.

Figure 5 shows the total strain energy release rate at the crack tip B outside the overlap for the two joints loaded by the far-field stress 220 MPa. It is seen that for both unidirectional and cross-ply adherends, the strain energy release rate at the crack tip B is

substantially smaller compared to the energy release at the crack tip *A*. The energy dissipates with the increasing delamination length.

Figure 4. Variation of strain energy release rate at crack tip *A* with crack length: unidirectional (a) and cross-ply (b) adherends

Figure 5. Variation of strain energy release rate at crack tip *B* with crack length: unidirectional (a) and cross-ply (b) adherends

Figure 6 shows the variation of the strain energy release rate at the crack tip *A* when the delamination is located between the second and third plies in the unidirectional and cross-ply adherends. It is seen that the strain energy release rate is smaller compared to the case when the delamination is located between the first and second plies (Figure 5). Same effect is observed for the strain energy release rate at the crack tip *B*.

Figure 6. Variation of strain energy release rate at crack tip *A* with crack length: crack located between second and third plies of unidirectional (a) and cross-ply (b) adherends

Figure 7 shows the variation of the maximum strain energy release rate at the crack tip A with delamination depth. It is seen that, in both cases, the maximum strain energy release rate decreases with the delamination depth. The maximum strain energy release rates in the unidirectional and cross-ply joints become closer as delamination depth increases.

Figure 7. Variation of maximum strain energy release rate at crack tip A with depth of crack location for unidirectional (a) and cross-ply (b) adherends

Overall, the analysis shows that the single lap adhesive composite joints are delamination tolerant. In all cases studied, the strain energy release rate decreased as delamination length increased. The maximum strain energy release rate in the joints with cross-ply adherends was greater than that in the joints with unidirectional adherends. The maximum strain energy release rate at the crack tip inside the overlap section decreased as delamination depth increased.

EXPERIMENTAL VERIFICATION

Single lap adhesive composite joints were manufactured from high-temperature, Boeing certified Hexcel T2G_190-12"-F263 graphite/epoxy prepreg and Cytec 300-2M adhesive film. Unidirectional $[0]_6$ and cross-ply $[0/90/0]_8$ lay-ups were utilized. The joint panels were prepared by the secondary curing using manufacturer recommended curing cycles. The panels were cut into specimens by a high speed diamond saw. The specimen geometry is shown in Figure 8. The overlap length was 60 mm. Delaminations were introduced into adherends by a thin Teflon film inserted during manufacturing. Location of the delamination tip in the overlap section was varied.

Figure 8. Geometry of a single lap joint specimen

Mechanical testing was performed on a servohydraulic MTS testing machine retrofitted by an Instron digital test control and data acquisition system. On-line video microscopy was used to characterize delamination growth (Figure 9).

Figure 9. Experimental set-up

initial $l_A \approx 0$

initial $l_A \approx 0.6$ mm

initial $l_A \approx 1.0$ mm

initial $l_A \approx 1.5$ mm

Figure 10. Delamination growth in unidirectional adherends with various initial crack length (far-field stress 220 MPa)

Figure 10 compares the growth of delamination between the first and second plies in four unidirectional joints with different initial crack tip location. All joints were loaded to the far-field tensile stress 220 MPa. It is seen that the crack lengths appears independent of the initial crack tip position and is about 1.5 mm in all four cases tested. Figure 11 compares the delaminations between the first and second plies in cross-ply joints with different initial crack tip location. These joints were also loaded to 220 MPa. It is seen that the crack lengths is independent of the initial crack tip position and is about 0.75 mm.

initial $l_A \gg 0$

initial $l_A \gg 0.25$ mm

Figure 11. Delamination growth in cross-ply adherends with various initial crack length (far-field stress 220 MPa)

Figure 12. Delamination growth in unidirectional adherend: crack located between the second and third ply (initial $l_A \gg 0$; far-field stress 220 MPa)

Figure 12 shows the growth of delamination located between the second and third plies in the unidirectional adherend. It is seen that the crack length at the far-field stress 220 MPa is smaller than in the case of delamination located between the first and second plies (Figure 10). Overall, the experimental results corroborate well with the theoretical predictions.

CONCLUSIONS

A model for the calculation of the strain energy release rate in adhesive joints with arbitrary cracked laminated adherends was developed and experimentally verified. The analysis showed that single lap joints are delamination tolerant. In all cases studied, the strain energy release rate decreased as the crack length increased. The maximum strain energy release rate in the joints with cross-ply adherends was greater than the rate in the joints with unidirectional adherends; however, the dissipation of energy with the crack growth was also stronger. The maximum strain energy release rate at the crack tip inside the overlap section decreased as the depth of crack increased. Experimental observations of the behavior of joints with different initial crack lengths corroborated with the theoretical predictions.

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